

Title: PredictMod: A Platform for Predicting Medical Intervention Outcomes and Sharing Custom ML/AI Models

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ABSTRACT

Machine learning/artificial intelligence (ML/AI) based predictive modeling is becoming increasingly popular in healthcare, particularly within the scope of precision medicine. Models based on patient data are effective tools for clinical decision-making, as well as impactful methods for researchers to expand on existing scientific and clinical understanding of biomarkers and biological pathways. We present PredictMod, an open-license platform for users to query, run, and publish electronic medical records and omics-based intervention outcome (responder vs. non-responder) prediction models. The platform currently hosts several intervention outcome prediction models that utilize varied data types, conditions, and interventions, offering users insight into the kinds of information required to develop such models. Model-specific graphs and charts such as confusion matrices and feature importance facilitate user understanding of model output. Our model-creation pipeline ensures comprehensive documentation using BioCompute Objects. The platform allows researchers in conjunction with clinicians to generate models using data from publications or their datasets and apply them to predict intervention outcomes for new patients or samples. The workflow includes support for synthetic data generation through external code, which must be downloaded and run locally. This enables augmentation of underrepresented categories, helping to balance responder and non-responder groups and enhance model reliability. PredictMod is particularly suited for small datasets, which are common in biological research. By providing a framework for pilot studies, the platform facilitates early-stage insights, helping researchers justify larger-scale data collection efforts. With its versatility and accessibility, PredictMod can advance biomedical research and precision clinical medicine by lowering technical barriers and fostering data-driven discovery approaches at the early stages of hypothesis generation using AI/ML.

BACKGROUND

Clinical relevance of intervention outcome prediction modeling

Predictive modeling is a common machine-learning (ML) approach used in the fields of economics, medicine, and data science. This subset of artificial intelligence (AI) involves the use of statistical algorithms to identify patterns within data that can be used to make predictions and identify relationships between variables¹⁻³. Within the context of precision medicine, classification models have become increasingly popular as tools to support clinical decision-making⁴⁻⁶. These models have widespread applicability across diverse medical specialties as they can utilize patient-specific data from electronic medical records (EMR), biological samples, and wearable technology to provide insight into the optimal timing and direction of proposed interventions^{7, 8}.

When prescribing treatments or interventions, clinicians must determine the necessity of a specific treatment, the optimal timing of the desired intervention, or whether a different approach is better suited for the patient. While clinician judgment is pivotal in guiding treatment decisions, predictive models can both validate initial judgments and expand clinical perspectives to provide insights into relevant biomarkers and biological pathways^{9, 10}. Several of the clinician's decisions and treatment plans are based on the prediction of disease progression, therefore, intervention outcome prediction (responder vs. non-responder) tools in clinical contexts are valuable. Though clinical decision support tools are a popular predictive modeling tool, effective utilization of these resources for therapeutic clinical decision making requires extensive integration into secure EMR systems¹¹.

We have created PredictMod¹², an open-license platform that enhances access to intervention outcome prediction models for clinicians and researchers, while also helping them understand and apply these models to improve intervention outcomes. The tool does not store any user data that is uploaded to get predictions. This platform is unique in several ways.

Novelty and innovation of the tool and design

PredictMod incorporates multiple data types. We have trained and integrated into the platform several EMR and omics (e.g. metagenomics, transcriptomics, glycomics data) models that can predict progression of prediabetes (preDM) to Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), progression of epilepsy, and cancer diagnosis and management¹³⁻¹⁹. We streamline robust ML pipeline elements such as data harmonization, mapping, and quality control (QC), allowing for more focused efforts on model training processes. The user interface (UI) is tailored to multiple distinct user personas, such as clinicians and researchers. It utilizes JavaScript and Python frameworks, along with Docker containers, to provide a fluid, intuitive user interface and robust security. These technologies provide an agile approach to incorporating user feedback, continuously improving accessibility. If needed, users can deploy the Docker containers and run the entire system within their firewall, ensuring both portability and security.

PredictMod is a collaborative space for researchers to upload their models. These models are freely available to users and commercial entities under the CC BY 4.0 license. Users seeking only

outcome predictions can upload their data, provided a matching model is available. Since no data is stored, users can securely obtain prediction results without concerns about data retention.

The platform supports models that incorporate tools such as the SHapely Additive exPlanation (SHAP)²⁰ to render model-agnostic explanations of intervention outcome predictions for a given input. Through the use of BioCompute Objects (BCOs), PredictMod ensures explainable, standardized documentation of ML pipelines. BCOs are an Institute for Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE) standard currently in use by the United States (US) Food and Drug Administration (FDA), and their adoption fosters transparency and reproducibility^{21, 22}.

The goal of this platform is to provide users with a structured mechanism to extract data from publications (or their datasets) where dataset sizes are often small and build predictive models for broader accessibility. These users, referred to as *model submitters*, contribute models to the platform. *Model users*, on the other hand, can browse available models and upload their data to obtain outcome predictions. By focusing on intervention outcome prediction, specifically distinguishing responders from non-responders, we encourage researchers to systematically collect pre-intervention data from patients, model organisms, or cell lines. Additionally, we emphasize the importance of clearly documenting responder and non-responder classifications in publications so that model submitters can use such data to create models. This straightforward approach has the potential to generate highly valuable datasets that can significantly enhance intervention strategies, reduce unnecessary experimentation, and optimize research funds usage.

CONSTRUCTION AND CONTENT

Software configuration

The PredictMod user interface (UI) is designed to be approachable to a wide range of users, spanning researchers to clinicians. Disclaimers are in place to explicitly state that this platform cannot be used in a clinical setting for patient diagnosis or treatment. Such usage would require additional levels of testing and authorization. The tool is written using a modern technology stack consisting of components using various frameworks in both Python (e.g. scikit-learn²³, Django²⁴, Flask²⁵, and others) and JavaScript (e.g. Vue²⁶, Vuetify²⁷, and Vite²⁸, and others). This basic software design allows rapid development as well as support of creating distinct user experiences.

The UI and supporting backend architecture are also designed with speed and scalability as core components. The UI runs locally on the browser, interacting directly with the user. When server interactions are required, such as login or submitting data for modeling, a manager process on the PredictMod server triages work requirements and dispatches work as appropriate. Specifically, light work such as credential management is handled immediately, while more intensive work is dispatched to workers in a round-robin fashion. All services are treated as independent microservices through containerization within docker²⁹ containers.

Specifically, one service (the “entrypoint”) runs as a reverse proxy to the login service, as well as serving the PredictMod UI pages as text files to newly-arrived users. A second service (“middleware”), accessed only through the reverse proxy, handles the user and model information

database and maintains a list of backend services with a map of the model, data type, and network location of available modeling resources. Finally, a third set of services (“models”) exists to handle potentially compute-intensive models. These services are only network-accessible to the middleware and are registered with the middleware upon system startup. When users submit jobs for modeling, the middleware receives the request and routes it directly to a container running the appropriate service. In case sufficient service containers are not available, the work is enqueued and processed when resources become available. In future development, additional resources may be brought up and registered with the middleware if user workloads are sufficiently demanding. This overall architecture allows sufficient modularity to rapidly scale the system to support many thousands of simultaneous, intensive workloads if needed.

The UI is configured to handle a single combination of condition, clinical intervention, and input data to an appropriate model. For example, one of the first models (“MDCIone Diet Counseling”) supported on the platform was trained using EMR data from a cohort of US Veterans Affairs (VA) patients. The data is housed in an internal cloud analytics environment that contains a partial copy of the VA Corporate Data Warehouse. We derived synthetic patient data using commercial software³⁰. The cohort contained over 450,000 patients with a preDM diagnosis and over 2.1 million patients with a confirmed T2DM diagnosis. The data were filtered for samples where records indicated patients had been treated for preDM with a dietary counseling and surveillance (International Classification of Diseases, 10th Revision (ICD-10)³¹ Z71.3) intervention prescribed by the clinician. Patients were described as “Responder” to treatment with this intervention if, after 6 months, they exhibited a 5% or greater reduction in weight; and “Non-Responder” otherwise. The model inputs are fully described by the combination of condition (preDM), intervention (dietary counseling), and form of clinical data used (EMR). We endeavor to allow future models to provide some flexibility in both intervention and data inputs. Flexibility in interventions may be particularly promising. For example, a motivating use case would be a clinician with EMR data available who is then able to use PredictMod to simultaneously make intervention outcome predictions for that patient across multiple possible interventions and treatment-scenarios (i.e. lifestyle interventions, medication treatments, or even surgical interventions). Given a set of models with good performance, choosing the most promising intervention immediately would be invaluable.

Methods for data ingestion

Proper data ingestion practices are crucial in order to ensure accurate and comprehensive data collection. This was achieved by leveraging data dictionaries and mapping for each curated dataset. The data dictionaries developed for PredictMod utilize Logical Observation Identifiers Names and Codes (LOINC)³² as their primary ontological identifier, given its wide use regarding health measurements, alongside the ICD-10, Systemized Nomenclature of Medicine (SNOMED)³³, and Current Procedural Terminology (CPT)³⁴ codes. Recognizing the potential for multiple terminologies for a single measurement, we engaged in thorough research and collaborated closely with clinical professionals to identify the most appropriate code for each measurement. The data mapping file helps maintain consistency by clearly defining relationships between data elements from different sources or formats to ensure accurate integration and interpretation across datasets. Leveraging data dictionaries and data mapping was particularly beneficial as we harmonized information from multiple resources, including omics datasets, EMR

platforms, scientific literature, and synthetic patient databases. Here we describe our processes for curating data and training several of the initial models for inclusion in the PredictMod platform.

Data quality control

A critical element of our data ingestion protocol is the QC of raw data. This step is crucial to improve the reliability of model training, as it helps to eliminate errors, reduce noise, and ensure the accuracy and consistency of the dataset. Data QC typically begins with assessing null values, evaluating class imbalance, and identifying extraneous variables. Classification algorithms are typically capable of handling missing values, but K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) imputation can be used when only a small portion of data is missing to improve data completeness and model reliability³⁵. Classification algorithms can also handle minor class imbalances, but when the imbalance is substantial, resampling methods such as Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique (SMOTE) or leave-one-out cross-validation (LOOCV) were applied to improve model performance^{36, 37}. Additionally, collaboration with medical experts was essential in determining whether to exclude certain extraneous variables. QC procedures also emphasize the removal of censored data to reduce noise and ensure that data types, units, and value ranges align with the standards defined in the data dictionary and mapping documents.

Augmenting real data with synthetic data

In biomedical research, small sample sizes often pose challenges for developing robust machine learning models and evaluating computational scalability. To overcome this limitation, we have designed an algorithm that utilizes conditional Generative Adversarial Networks (cGANs) to generate synthetic data, effectively expanding available datasets. While synthetic data may not always improve model accuracy, it provides researchers with the ability to assess computational efficiency such as training and inference times on larger datasets. Additionally, it enables the augmentation of underrepresented classes in binary classification tasks, helping to balance datasets and improve model evaluation as implemented in SMOTE. As real-world data becomes available, users can compare its quality against the generated synthetic data to evaluate its utility.

Various algorithms have been employed to generate synthetic biomedical data, addressing limitations in sample size for machine learning applications. For example, one study developed a method to generate synthetic populations from matched case-control data ($n = 180$ pairs) using multivariate kernel density estimations (KDEs) with constrained bandwidth matrices, effectively expanding datasets for more reliable modeling³⁸. More recently, generative AI techniques such as ESOM (Emergent Self-Organizing Maps) - based augmentation, which concentrates new points around existing data, enhancing their utility for downstream analysis³⁹. ESOM-based augmentation does appear to be a viable alternative to producing synthetic data, also capable of capturing global and local features, but can have a higher time complexity and computation costs compared to certain GAN architectures³⁹.

Our GAN-based method achieves more realistic data compared to other generative approaches by leveraging a feature learning approach, wherein the generator iteratively refines its output in response to feedback from the discriminator. The cGANs utilize patient data tags as conditional inputs such as responder/non-responder status during the synthesis of new data. The original

GAN architecture does not use tags/conditions and reduces its ability to accurately represent original data. Other traditional generative models such as Variational Autoencoders (VAEs), they may be more useful in capturing outliers and noise, but can suffer from lower sample sharpness and not capture complex data⁴⁰. GANs implicitly learn complex data distributions through the competitive optimization between the generator and discriminator. This allows them to capture high-dimensional dependencies and generate more realistic outputs without requiring explicit density estimation from the data. However, GANs can suffer from mode collapse, where generators produce limited, highly similar outputs instead of capturing the full range of the target data distribution⁴¹. Despite advancements in GAN-generated medical data, validation metrics such as Wasserstein metric or negative log-likelihood cannot guarantee the generated medical data will retain patient or cohort-wide characteristics essential for building predictive outcome models⁴².

For a robust validation approach, five different metrics were used to compare the synthetic data to their original counterpart: Mean Difference, Standard Deviation Difference, Pairwise Euclidean Distance, Feature Correlation, and Mean Kolmogorov-Smirnov (KS) Test P-Value. These metrics were used for the following methods for comparison: SMOTE, GAN, and cGAN. The cGAN model better preserves statistical relationships while maintaining greater sample diversity than SMOTE without losing too much realism, than the GAN achieved.

Use of MDClone synthetic data source

MDClone ADAMS Platform³⁰ is a self-service data analytics platform that has a collaboration with the VA and enables healthcare collaboration, research, and innovation. It provides synthetic datasets that are based on real patient data. Synthetic data comprises a novel population with similar statistical characteristics and intervariable correlations as the population data without including any original patient data points⁴³. This allows for data transfer internally and externally without compromising any sensitive personally identifiable information (PII). The synthetic dataset is used to train advanced algorithms within the PredictMod application, enabling predictions of treatment outcomes for patients with preDM or T2DM in response to interventions that typically include lifestyle changes or medication. All synthetic datasets are statistically similar to the source VA patient datasets housed in the MDClone ADAMS Platform, and a comparison report is carefully reviewed as part of the data harmonization process.

The process of query building involves creating a cohort of interest. The MDClone Diet Counseling cohort included patients at least 18 years old with a preDM diagnosis and a Body Mass Index (BMI) at or above 30. For individuals that satisfied these criteria and had undergone drug or lifestyle intervention, variables of interest including weight, BMI, blood pressure, and Hemoglobin A1c (HbA1C) collected less than six months prior to intervention were added to the queries and extracted. If multiple lab results within the six-month window were available, the most recent one prior to the start of the intervention was used. Variables of interest were identified and incorporated through targeted keyword searches and LOINC code mapping to enhance data capture. A parameter was also set to extract the patients' weight 9-12 months following intervention and identify those who experienced a 5% reduction in weight from baseline ("Responders").

Methods for model training and validation

Our model training workflow for each model involves using refined EMR and omics datasets to uncover predictive signals indicative of intervention outcomes before their commencement. An initial training phase using a stratified data split is conducted to observe the models' decision-making patterns before additional optimization or tuning. Further, if needed hyperparameter tuning is conducted to account for overfitting and to optimize generalizability. Model QC involves validating each model against the current literature and guidance by medical and ML experts. Techniques such as feature importance analysis, SHAP, and examination of other metrics of explainable AI are also employed to assess the alignment of each model's output decisions with current scientific understanding^{44, 45}. After training, validation, and thorough documentation of the model pipeline, the models are integrated into the PredictMod platform. The corresponding READMEs and BCOs are then made available in the PredictMod GitHub repository.

Use of BCOs

BioCompute Objects were created as an IEEE standard for standardizing and sharing computations and analyses. In PredictMod, BCOs are used to fully describe all details of a model, including the data set used for training and associated provenance, model type and associated hyperparameters used to create the model, software requirements, and any other information required to fully replicate the model. Within the platform, model authors are given expansive freedom in creating the BCO for a description of submitted models. The only requisite for the complete BCO - or set of BCOs - is that all information required to recreate the model, including provenance, is contained within the BCO.

Creating BCO pipelines is crucial for enhancing transparency, reproducibility, and accountability in scientific processes, particularly in fields like bioinformatics and healthcare. For each model we create, there is a pipeline to document each step from data preprocessing to model evaluation, ensuring that every decision and transformation is clearly defined and accessible. This documentation not only facilitates future edits and refinements by providing a clear roadmap, but also enables peer review and validation of methodologies. By adhering to BCO standards, researchers and practitioners can confidently reproduce results, validate findings, and collaborate effectively, thereby advancing scientific rigor and trustworthiness in computational biology and related disciplines. Our pipelines leverage standardized preprocessing, rigorous model training, and thorough evaluation to create an intervention outcome prediction model, supporting reproducibility and transparency in its approach.

Portability

PredictMod is designed for portability and deployment flexibility. The platform is containerized using Docker, enabling seamless deployment across diverse environments, including institutional servers, commercial cloud providers, and secure on-premise systems. This ensures compatibility with various IT infrastructures and supports scalable execution.

USAGE AND UTILITY

Platform overview

PredictMod empowers researchers and clinicians with limited experience in bioinformatics to leverage the power of predictive modeling. Currently, the platform houses 12 intervention outcome prediction models with the infrastructure to support new model creation and submission. Models are accessed through the query builder, where users can select the condition, intervention, and data type of interest and upload a single-patient sample file to obtain an intervention outcome prediction result. The model output consists of the result statement, indicating whether a patient is considered a “Responder” or “Non-Responder” to the chosen intervention. In addition, model-specific graphs and/or charts, such as confusion matrices and relevant features are shown, highlighting important features or pathways the model used to make its decision. This improves explainability and clinician trust in the model’s performance. The visuals shown vary based on the specific model and is left to the discretion of the model creator. To address data security concerns, uploading patient data for prediction requires login access.

Tailored interfaces for researchers and clinicians

We have developed several user stories to describe the most likely sets of users of the PredictMod platform. To develop these stories, we held a series of onsite and virtual design thinking workshops with clinicians, researchers, students, informaticians, and software engineers. We have broken these sets into “clinicians” and “researchers”. Specifically, we anticipate that clinicians will wish to take advantage of the modeling capabilities to incorporate AI/ML-bolstered information from PredictMod to inform their clinical judgement, based on relevant clinical lab tests, patient histories, etc. The clinician portal is designed to provide a clean, unambiguous display of information as produced by the model. Where multiple models exist for one set of conditions and interventions, we endeavor to keep the UI uncluttered while providing the “best” model results, based on a particular patient’s circumstances. Future releases of the software will aim to allow output to contrast outputs from the various models.

In contrast to the clinician view, the researcher view of the PredictMod platform is intended to allow deep introspection of the models, particularly the inner workings of what each model does. As the platform matures, we anticipate that this will allow researchers to inspect not just the model, but also work on explaining why certain features of data inputs may have outsized impact on predictions. Thus, the platform allows the research community to collaboratively improve the models while continuing to compete with newly submitted data.

‘Publish a model’ tool

New tool submission for model publication follows a standardized procedure. Specifically, new models will be required to submit documentation, exemplar data to confirm inputs and outputs, and BCO(s) that fully enumerate the provenance of all components of the model. Model QC will be conducted before the models will be available on the platform. The model must also be containerized for deployment within the PredictMod platform. Generally, models must be submitted as a dockerized web service, or series of dockerized web services if the model presents a substantial computational workload. Currently, the PredictMod team may provide assistance in containerization of a model, but as the platform matures we expect to fully hand off that task to future modelers, with support from thorough documentation provided by the PredictMod platform.

Interpretation of prediction results

Explainable AI is of paramount importance for the PredictMod platform. In general, modern AI and ML algorithms are often “black boxes,” with inscrutable connections between input features and the resulting output. In a clinical setting, these artifacts may not just make the model less trustworthy but could potentially mislead a clinician’s professional judgment. Thus, the PredictMod platform supports models that implement SHAP, a state-of-the-art set of tools developed to allow introspection into any AI algorithms, including black-box models. The resulting introspection is presented to the user with simple, easy-to-understand diagrams that trace the contribution of various input features to the associated output values. As the PredictMod platform continues to grow, we anticipate continued additions of introspection tools such as SHAP to support the expanding ecosystem of AI and ML tools. Detailed resource pages are available to users, where they can look into the specifics of data sources, algorithm selection, model performance, and predictive features to make informed interpretations of model results.

AI/ML tutorial

The AI/ML tutorial guides users through the model pipeline, allowing them to train and improve models using their own data⁴⁶. The tutorial encompasses relevant software installation, understanding input and output files, training and comparing the performance of multiple machine learning models, and enhancement techniques such as hyperparameter tuning and cross-validation. This tutorial is accessible from the PredictMod platform.

Several other resources are available on the PredictMod site, including *About*, *Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ)*, *Contact*, and *Help* pages. These resources provide detailed information on how to use the query builder, current and anticipated models, FAQ, and how to contact the team. The *Models* page provides a comprehensive view of all released models and their versions. The *Search* feature allows users to quickly identify relevant models based on their name, condition, intervention, or data type.

Automated machine learning training and sampling pipeline

We have created an automated model training pipeline for researchers who have a significant collection of data without the programming expertise required to create and train such models. Such researchers may use this automated pipeline to directly upload data. Upon upload of training data, the PredictMod platform performs several consecutive steps.

Next, given an appropriately formatted data set that has all such errors removed, the platform provides the user results from several ML and statistical algorithms to provide both additional insight into the data and intervention outcome prediction models for use with future data points. Specifically, the user is given Principal Component Analysis (PCA) clustering outputs as a means for the user to explore for clear patterns in the data or other such low-hanging fruit. The user is also provided trained models, and corresponding confusion matrices and Receiver Operator Characteristic (ROC) curve analysis for a diverse family of ML models, including Random Forest, Decision Tree Classifiers, Support Vector Machines, Logistic Regression, and Boosting algorithms⁴⁷⁻⁵¹. The trained models are retained within the PredictMod platform for the user to

further introspect, use with additional data points, download, or eventually publish to the broader PredictMod ecosystem.

Additional resources for each algorithm are provided to the user for each resulting model in the form of links to both algorithm descriptions and original source references that describe the underlying algorithms.

Tool availability

The software, along with usage instructions, is available through the project repository⁵². The platform is freely accessible at <https://hivelab.biochemistry.gwu.edu/predictmod>.

Example usage

A potential user would be prompted to log in before submitting a query. Once logged in, they can navigate to the query builder and select the desired condition, intervention, and data type. They are then prompted to upload a file to use for the intervention outcome prediction. All models have an example file available for download, so a new user can practice the tool with an example file, or use the formatting as a template for their own sample data. Once the file is uploaded, a user will select 'Submit & Analyze' and obtain a result within seconds. The density of model output varies by user, with researchers having the most information and clinicians having the simplest view. The user can then choose to run another prediction, which will reset the query builder selection and allow them to explore other models. No personal health information is stored on the PredictMod website, and users cannot save past predictions within the site.

Clinicians can use the query builder to run multiple predictions for different interventions for a single patient. This access to patient-level prediction results for various interventions assists clinicians in comparing the effectiveness of said treatments and ultimately, making the best treatment decision. For example, for a patient with a preDM diagnosis who is at risk of progressing to T2DM, a clinician can compare dietary options, exercise or lifestyle changes, medication-based interventions, or even bariatric surgery using existing models. An alternative view of each model is available, principally intended for use by researchers more interested in individual models, but available to all users. In these views, documentation of each model in the platform is rendered alongside metadata about the model, e.g. the post-training confusion matrix and a list of the most relevant features for the model. As with the 'Query Builder' views, users are presented with an interface to download example files, upload new sample files, and obtain prediction results from each model on the platform.

CONCLUSION

While several ML algorithms and studies exist for biomedical applications ranging from disease progression to outcome prediction^{53, 54}, none, to the best of our knowledge, currently offer an integrated, user-friendly system specifically designed for intervention outcome modeling that supports community contributions and iterative model development. In summary, we have presented a novel approach to intervention-based predictive modeling that integrates multiple data types, distinct user personas, collaboration between researchers, clinicians, and standardized, reproducible documentation. We leverage synthetic data to enhance the dataset

and privacy protection, which distinguishes our tool from conventional methods. The synthetic data also plays a crucial role in validating models derived from real patient data. While models developed from limited data may not achieve optimal performance, this approach enables users to contribute their own models and supports iterative refinement as new data becomes available, fostering continuous improvement over time. We hope that the collaborative nature of PredictMod extends the usefulness of the platform and provides an expansive selection for researcher and clinicians to use. The platform provides a model-agnostic approach for users, allowing for multiple models to overlap among conditions and interventions.

Availability and requirements:

Project name: PredictMod

Project home page: <https://hivelab.biochemistry.gwu.edu/predictmod>

Operating system(s): Platform independent

Programming language: JavaScript & Python

Other requirements: None

License: CC BY 4.0

Any restrictions to use by non-academics: None

Abbreviations:

ML: Machine Learning

AI: Artificial Intelligence

EMR: Electronic Medical Records

preDM: Prediabetes

T2DM: Type II Diabetes Mellitus

QC: Quality Control

UI: User Interface

SHAP: Shapely Additive Explanation

BCO: BioCompute Object

IEEE: Institute for Electrical and Electronics Engineers

US: United States

ICD-10: International Classification of Diseases, 10th Revision

LOINC: Logical Observation Identifiers Names and Codes

SNOMED: Systemized Nomenclature of Medicine

CPT: Current Procedural Terminology

BMI: Body Mass Index

PII: personally identifiable information

KNN: K-Nearest Neighbors

SMOTE: Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique

LOOCV: Leave-one-out cross-validation

GANs: Generative Adversarial Networks

KDEs: Kernel Density Estimations

ESOM: Emergent Self-Organizing Maps

VAEs: Variational Autoencoders

BCE: Binary Cross-Entropy
VA: Veterans Administration
PCA: Principal Component Analysis
t-SNE: t-distributed stochastic neighbor embedding
ROC: Receiver Operator Characteristic

Declarations

Ethics Approval and Consent to Participate: Not applicable.

Consent for Publication: Not applicable.

Availability of Data and Materials: Software and documentation is available through the project repository (<https://github.com/GW-HIVE/PredictMod>).

Competing Interests: The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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Figure 1

Figure 1. User interface structure. Figure 1 illustrates how users interact with the PredictMod user interface, as well as the docker infrastructure. The docker infrastructure is composed of three components: the frontend, middleware, and analytical backend, providing both speed and scalability.

Figure 2

Figure 2. PredictMod ML pipeline and integration workflow. Figure 2 illustrates the ML pipeline, from data ingestion through platform integration. Our existing models are sourced from both EMR and omics data, and undergo data harmonization and QC prior to model training and validation. Once validated, the entire pipeline is documented in a BCO and compiled into a docker container for platform integration.

Figure 3

Figure 3. Prediction workflow. Figure 3 illustrates how a user would build a query and obtain a prediction result, based on single-patient data. All models on the platform follow this workflow. In addition to the query builder, users can select a model through a search or through the 'Models' page and run a prediction from there.

Figure 4

Figure 4. PredictMod platform landing page. Figure 4 provides a screenshot of the PredictMod landing page, which provides information on registering, exploring models, version details, and model statistics.